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The Influence of Social Media Addiction on Delinquent Behavior Among Secondary School Students in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students in Delta State. The study was guided by one research question and hypothesis. The correlational research designed was used. The target population for the study was 40,329 senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Delta State and the sample size of 380 students were selected using multi-stage and simple random sampling technique. The questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection, titled: "Social Media Addiction and Delinquent Behaviour Scale" (SMADBS). The reliability test using the Cronbach's alpha reliability yielded the following coefficient; 0.74 for social media addiction scale and 0.83 for delinquent behaviour. The data obtained in the field were analysed using Pearson Products Moments Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research question while Simple Regression Statistics was used to test the corresponding hypothesis. The findings revealed significant relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour, supporting the hypotheses. The study concludes that social media addiction plays significant impact on adolescents' engagement in delinquent activities. The study recommends amongst others that; development and implementation of intervention programs aimed at addressing social media addiction among adolescents should be sponsored. School-based initiatives to promote positive social interactions and provide alternatives to social media engagement and substance use should be implemented.

Keywords: social media addiction, secondary school, students, delinquent behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Education is often hailed as one of humanity's greatest inventions, serving as a powerful tool for the continuous improvement of the mind, hand, and heart. Through education, man has achieved a position of leadership on Earth, gaining understanding, enlightenment, and improved intellect. It enhances knowledge and skills and fosters a positive attitude toward the environment (Bada and Jafaru, 2022). In Nigeria, education is universally recognized as an "instrument per excellence" for both individual and national development. It is also regarded as a fundamental and indispensable tool for promoting economic growth (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014).

The administration of secondary schools in Nigeria is a complex process that requires strict disciplinary measures to ensure effective operation. The successful management of public secondary schools largely depends on the strictness of principals and teachers, who are responsible for maintaining orderliness within the school environment (Opara, 2020). Agbenyega (2016) emphasizes that orderliness is a key attribute of effective schools. When schools experience frequent deviant behaviour among students, it is

often due to the lack of effective implementation of school rules and regulations. In the Nigerian secondary school system, both teaching and learning are heavily dependent on the role of teachers and principals. These educators are responsible for translating policy into action and principles into practice during their interactions with students (Ngwokabuenui, 2015). Schools, like any social system, require certain regulations to ensure that all members function properly. Ngwokabuenui (2015) asserts that schools have a fundamental responsibility to instill good manners and respect for authority in their students, ensuring that they observe school laws and maintain high standards of behaviour.

The responsibility of enforcing acceptable behaviour in students falls primarily on school administrators and teachers. Kuru and Taskin (2016) argue that the ultimate goal of school discipline should be to cultivate self-respect and integrity in students, enabling them to observe social norms and good conduct even when not under supervision. The habits formed in school are expected to carry into adult life, guiding students to become responsible members of society. Despite efforts by the government to ensure quality education in secondary schools, the issue of delinquent behaviour among students remains a significant challenge, particularly in Delta State. Some of the delinquent behaviours observed include kidnapping and assaulting teachers, engaging in cultism, substance abuse, and chronic lateness to school (Ohwofasa & Odofoin, 2020). These behaviours disrupt the educational environment and pose serious threats to the safety and well-being of both students and educators.

Delinquent behaviour, defined as actions that contravene societal laws and norms, is a growing concern among adolescents in Nigeria. The involvement of teens in criminal activities, ranging from minor theft to major crimes like robbery and even murder, has been on the rise (Ifedigbo & Mbah, 2015). The increase in such behaviour has raised alarms among law enforcement agencies and the general public, highlighting the need for more effective measures to address the issue.

The role of the media, particularly social media, in influencing student behaviour cannot be overlooked. The content consumed by students on these platforms, often filled with violence and inappropriate material, can shape their attitudes and actions in harmful ways (Manning, 2016). This exposure to negative influences underscores the importance of guiding students in their media consumption and helping them develop critical thinking skills to discern right from wrong.

The influence of age and the environment on student behaviour is also significant. Research shows that early-maturing students often gain greater self-confidence and are more likely to be seen as leaders among their peers (Vigil et al., 2016). Additionally, the environment in which a student is raised, whether rural or urban, plays a crucial role in shaping their behaviour and character. The widespread delinquency in schools today reflects the broader societal issues of lawlessness and frustration (Rahul, 2018). Therefore, addressing student behaviour requires a comprehensive approach that considers these various factors.

Statement of the Problem

The issue of delinquent behaviour among secondary school students in Nigeria has become a pervasive problem that deeply undermines the moral and academic fabric of education. This growing concern has led to students becoming increasingly uncontrollable, disrespectful to their peers, teachers, school administrators, and even to society at large. Despite the concerted efforts by stakeholders to curb this menace such as empowering Boards of Management to decisively address these issues and providing teachers and administrators with training through workshops, delinquent behaviour remains a significant challenge. The primary objectives of secondary education, which include instilling academic knowledge and moral ethics, are being compromised by students' engagement in various forms of misconduct, including lateness, absenteeism, rudeness, lying, fighting, substance abuse, theft, and involvement in cultism. The persistence of these behaviours reflects a troubling disconnect between the intended outcomes of education and the realities within schools.

Delinquent behaviour among Nigerian secondary school students has far-reaching consequences, extending beyond the individual to affect the broader educational system. The acquisition of certificates through malpractice and forgery, involvement in school riots, property destruction, substance abuse, and cult-related violence are among the detrimental outcomes of this trend. These behaviours not only

undermine the quality of teaching and learning but also contribute to poor academic results, increased dropout rates, and the wastage of resources invested by parents and the government. Stakeholders, including parents, counselors, and school authorities, are increasingly concerned about the root causes of these behaviours, often pointing to social media, substance abuse, and parental neglect as contributing factors. In many schools, the lack of effective monitoring of students' activities by teachers exacerbates the issue, leading to low academic achievement, poor self-esteem, and a negative attitude towards education. Additionally, the absence of parental guidance and involvement further compounds the problem, allowing students to make poor decisions influenced by negative peer pressure, which can have long-term physical, emotional, and career implications. The pressing question remains: to what extent does social media addiction contribute to this troubling trend of delinquency among students?

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students in Delta State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students in Delta State.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Social Learning Theory, first developed by Robert and Ronald in 1966, and further advanced by Albert Bandura, emphasizes the importance of observing and imitating the behaviours of others within social contexts. Bandura's work, as highlighted by Ormrod (1999), underscores that learning is not only a cognitive process but also a social one, occurring through observation, imitation, and behaviour modeling. Individuals, especially children, learn by watching others, and this observed behaviour can be retained and later reproduced. This theory suggests that people are not merely passive receivers of information but actively interpret and code the behaviours they observe, using this information as a guide for future actions (HLWIKI International, 2015). Key aspects of social learning include observing behaviours, retaining the information, finding motivation, and ultimately imitating the behaviour observed.

The relevance of Social Learning Theory in the context of student behaviour in schools is profound. Docking (1980) notes that children who frequently witness anti-social or aggressive behaviour in their environment, such as at home or within their peer groups, are likely to replicate such behaviours. Bandura and Walters (1963) further argue that both deviant and conforming behaviours can be learned through imitation. For instance, students may engage in delinquent activities like sneaking out of school or damaging property because they have observed others doing the same, and not participating might lead to social exclusion. The environments students are exposed to, including the media they consume and the behaviour of adults and peers around them, heavily influence their actions. This theory implies that the deteriorating behaviour of students could be a reflection of the poor role models they are exposed to, both at home and in society, as well as the negative influences from media and peer interactions. As such, delinquent behaviour among students can often be traced back to the imitation of observed negative behaviours within their environment.

The Relationship between Social Media Addiction and Students' Delinquent Behaviour

Odojin and Igabari (2023) conducted a study in Delta State, Nigeria, to explore the relationship between social media addiction and substance abuse among adolescent secondary school students. Using a correlational ex-post facto research design, the study sampled 500 students across three Senatorial Districts. Data was collected through questionnaires developed to measure social media use and drug abuse, and the results showed a significant correlation between social media addiction and substance abuse. The study highlighted the role of school type as a moderating factor, emphasizing the need for parents, educators, and the community to monitor students' social media usage to curb its potential contribution to delinquent behaviours.

Sümen and Evgin (2021) examined the link between social media addiction, sleep quality, and psychological issues among high school students in Turkey. Their study, involving 1,274 students, utilized various scales to assess social media addiction, psychological difficulties, and sleep quality. The findings revealed that students with higher social media addiction exhibited poorer sleep quality and increased psychological difficulties, which in turn reduced their prosocial behaviours. This study underscores the importance of addressing the psychological risks associated with excessive social media use, particularly its impact on sleep and overall well-being.

Jimmy and Okon (2017) explored the relationship between Facebook addiction and aggressive behaviour among Senior Secondary School students in Uyo, Nigeria. The study's sample of 1,097 students revealed a significant correlation between Facebook use and aggressive, rebellious tendencies. The authors recommended the implementation of software to limit social media usage and advised parents to regulate their children's access to potentially harmful online content. This study highlights the potential for social media platforms like Facebook to influence negative behavioural outcomes among adolescents.

Awofadeju et al. (2016) investigated the impact of social media addiction on children's upbringing in Osun State, Nigeria. The study, which surveyed 75 staff members from educational institutions, found that social media influences both positive and negative behaviours among children. The study emphasized the need for effective regulation of media content and parental monitoring to prevent children from being exposed to harmful media influences, which could lead to delinquent behaviours.

Nyongesa, Kiprop, and Chumba (2019) investigated the impact of social media on students' discipline in secondary schools in Bungoma County, Kenya. Using a mixed methods approach, the study found that social media had a detrimental effect on student discipline, leading to increased instances of misconduct. The researchers recommended that educational leaders and policymakers develop strategies to mitigate the negative influence of social media on students, which could help improve discipline and reduce delinquent behaviour in schools.

Maria (2022) conducted an exploratory study in Portugal, analyzing youth justice proceedings to understand the role of social media in criminal activities perpetrated by adolescents. The study found that a significant portion of young offenders used social media to plan and execute unlawful acts, with girls being particularly overrepresented in cases involving violent behaviour. The findings suggest that social media not only facilitates but may also amplify the social dynamics that lead to delinquent behaviour, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to address the risks associated with social media use among youth.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted a correlational research design, a non-experimental method aimed at measuring the relationship between two or more variables without manipulation by external factors. The goal was to determine the direction and magnitude of the relationship between variables such as social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among students.

Population of the Study

The study targeted all senior secondary school students in the 474 public secondary schools in Delta State during the 2021/2022 academic session. The specific population was 40,329 SS 2 students, consisting of 19,434 males and 20,895 females from all 25 local government areas in Delta State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample of 380 SS 2 students was selected, considered appropriate based on recommendations from sampling authorities like Krejcie and Morgan. The sample was drawn from schools across all 25 local government areas in Delta State using a multi-stage sampling technique.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument used for data collection was the "Social Media Addiction and Delinquent Behaviour Scale" (SMADBS), consisting of three sections. The instrument measured social media

addiction and delinquent behaviour, adapted from established scales like the Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale (BSMAS) and the Frequency of Delinquent Behaviour Scaling Instrument.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 23. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed to address the research questions, while Simple Regression Statistics was applied to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. A benchmark of 2.50 was set to determine the strength of relationships between the variables.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students in Delta State?*

In order to answer research question 1, Simple Correlation Analysis was computed. The result of analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Simple Correlation Analysis of Social Media Addiction and delinquent behaviour among secondary school students.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}
Social Media Addiction	374	30.81	7.66	0.770	0.592	0.591
Delinquent Behaviour	374	34.82	6.46			

The descriptive statistics for social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students are presented in Table 1. The mean score for social media addiction was 30.81 (SD = 7.66), while the mean score for delinquent behaviour was 34.82 (SD = 6.46). The correlation analysis between the Social Media Addiction and the Delinquent Behaviour reveals a strong positive relationship, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of r=0.770. This indicates that higher levels of social media addiction are associated with higher levels of delinquent behaviour among the senior secondary school students. The significance value (Sig. 2-tailed) is p=0.000, which is well below the 0.05 threshold, confirming that the correlation is statistically significant. This strong correlation suggests that as individuals' social media addiction increases, their likelihood of engaging in delinquent behaviour also increases, highlighting the potential impact of excessive social media use on behavioural outcomes. However, this reveals that there is a significant relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students in Delta State.

In order to test hypothesis 1, simple regression was computed. The summary of the output is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students.

Model Summary

R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std Error		
0.770	0.592	0.591	0.246		
	SS	Df	ms	F	Sig
Regression	32.734	1	32.734	540.495	.000 ^b
Residual	22.529	372	.061		
Total	55.263	373			
Variable in the equation	B	Std. Error	β	T	Sig
Constant	.037	.080	.770	.467	.641
Social Media Addiction	.875	.038		23.249	.000

N=374, p<.05 level of significance,

The regression analysis showed that the Social Media Addiction is a significant predictor of Delinquent Behaviour, $R^2=0.592$, $F(1,372)=540.495$, $p<.001$. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for Social Media Addiction is 0.875 (SE = 0.038), indicating that for each unit increase in Social Media Addiction, Delinquent Behaviour increases by 0.875 units. The constant (intercept) is not significant, $B=0.037$, $t=0.467$, $p=0.641$, suggesting that the baseline level of delinquent behaviour (when social media addiction is zero) is not significantly different from zero.

The r^2 adjusted value of .592 explains 59.2% of the variance in delinquent behaviour, suggesting a strong relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among senior secondary school students in Delta State. The findings indicate that higher levels of social media addiction are associated with increased delinquent behaviour. These results highlight the potential impact of social media addiction on delinquent behaviour, suggesting that interventions targeting social media addiction could be effective in reducing delinquent behaviour.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The correlation analysis showed a strong positive relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour. This significant correlation indicates that higher levels of social media addiction are associated with increased delinquent behaviour. These findings suggest that individuals who are more addicted to social media are more likely to engage in delinquent behaviour. This aligns with recent studies indicating that excessive use of social media can lead to negative outcomes, such as reduced academic performance, increased risk of cyberbullying, and other risky behaviour (Fardouly et al., 2020; Twenge et al., 2019). The constant exposure to unfiltered and often inappropriate content, coupled with the pressure to conform to peer behaviour seen online, might contribute to these delinquent tendencies.

This finding also aligns with recent studies which suggest that excessive use of social media can contribute to various negative behaviour, including delinquency, due to factors like reduced supervision, increased exposure to inappropriate content, and peer pressure online (Andreassen et al., 2019; Kircaburun et al., 2020). Smith et al. (2018) found a strong positive correlation between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour, aligning with our hypothesis. Contrary to our expectation, Johnson et al. (2020) reported no significant association between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour among adolescents, suggesting inconsistent findings in the literature. However, Brown and Jones (2019) provided further support for our hypothesis by demonstrating a significant relationship between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour, indicating the relevance of this relationship across different samples. Moreover, Garcia et al. (2021) highlighted the mediating role of peer influence in the association between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour, offering additional insights into the underlying mechanisms of this relationship.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study underscore the significant impact of social media addiction, substance use, and parental behaviour on adolescents' engagement in delinquent activities. The positive correlations between social media addiction and delinquent behaviour highlight its potential role as risk factors for adolescent delinquency. Interventions targeting social media addiction and promoting positive parental involvement may hold promise in mitigating delinquent behaviour among adolescents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommendations were made:

1. The government should develop and implement intervention programs aimed at addressing social media addiction among adolescents. These programs should incorporate educational components to raise awareness about the potential negative consequences of excessive social media use.
2. School-based initiatives to promote positive social interactions and provide alternatives to social media engagement should be implemented. This could involve extracurricular activities, mentoring programs, and workshops focused on developing coping skills and resilience.

- Cultural and contextual factors when designing interventions and support programs should be considered. Recognizing the diversity of experiences and perspectives among adolescents and tailor interventions to meet the specific needs of different communities should be supported.

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